

Tests of DES Charge Coupled Devices

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sota la direcció del Dr. Ramon Miquel i el Dr. Manel Martínez*

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1998 \dot{z} ? \longrightarrow Accelerates expansion

Riess et al. & Perlmutter et al.

found that the expansion rate of the universe is increasing with time studying type-Ia supernovae. 10-15% larger than expected

It changed completely our understanding of the universe and its components.

$$H^2(a) = H_0^2 \left[\Omega_M a^{-3} + \Omega_R a^{-4} \right]$$

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$$H^2(a) = H_0^2 \left[\Omega_M a^{-3} + \Omega_R a^{-4} + \Omega_{DE} a^{-3(1+w)} \right]$$

$$\Omega_{DE} = \frac{\rho_{DE}}{\rho_C} \quad P_{DE} = w\rho_{DE} \quad \rho_C = \frac{3H_0^2}{8\pi G}$$

Whatever mechanism causes the acceleration, we call it “dark energy”:

Einstein’s cosmological constant?

Some dynamical field (“quintessence”)?

Modifications to General Relativity?

Heavy Elements:
 $\Omega=0.0003$

Neutrinos (ν):
 $\Omega=0.0047$

Stars:
 $\Omega=0.005$

Free H & He:
 $\Omega=0.04$

Cold Dark Matter:
 $\Omega=0.25$

Dark Energy (Λ):
 $\Omega=0.70$

DARK ENERGY
SURVEY

Outline

- The Dark Energy Survey
- The SLAB
- DES CCDs
- Tests
- Conclusions

The Dark Energy Survey

- Optical & NIR survey
- Dark energy properties

$$P_{DE} = w\rho_{DE}$$

- 4m Blanco telescope (CTIO-NOAO)

The DECam

- CCD mosaic camera
- 3 sq deg field of view
- 62 LBNL CCDs (4k x 2k pixels)
- griZY filters
- 5000 sq deg
- 300 milion galaxies
- 15000 clusters
- 1200 SNIa

Galaxy clusters redshift distribution

Galaxy cluster density mass function (SPT)

SNela: Distance to standard candles

Weak lensing

Evolution of the distortions pattern

Correlation Vs redshift

Baryon acoustic oscillations

DES techniques

Galaxy clusters redshift distribution

Galaxy cluster density mass function (SPT)

Weak lensing

Evolution of the distortions pattern

Growth of density perturbations

Geometry of the Universe

Correlation Vs redshift

Baryon acoustic oscillations

SNela: Distance to standard candles

$$w(z) = w_0 + w_a(1 - a) = w_0 + w_a \frac{z}{1+z}$$

$$a = \frac{1}{1+z}$$

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$$I(x, y) = I_0 \cos^4(\theta)$$

- We used a photodiode (light intensity to electrical intensity)
- Measurements of the uniformity at different distances from the sphere
- 6cm transversally. Steps of 0.5cm

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x (in)	d = -3 cm	-2 cm	-1 cm	0 cm	1 cm	2 cm	3 cm
7	0.84	0.94	0.98	1.00	0.98	0.94	0.86
11	0.93	0.97	0.99	1.00	0.98	0.97	0.94
14	0.96	0.97	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.97	0.96

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The farther the photodiode is from the sphere, the better uniformity provides

Uniformity maps

measured spectrum

manufacturer spectrum

6cm x 6cm
surface

At 13 inches
from sphere

From 300 to
1100nm

Every 5nm

Uniformity maps

measured spectrum

manufacturer spectrum

6cm x 6cm surface

At 13 inches from sphere

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Characterization in absolute number of photons

- Absolute calibration in number of photons
- Photodiode in the other output sphere port
- Loss between the light emitted and the light detected
- This relative measurement is necessary to measure the QE in the future

$$R(\nu) = \frac{I_P(\nu)}{I_{CCD}(\nu)}$$

$$QE = \frac{P_{\text{int}}}{p_0 R(\nu)}$$

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To the cube

PD

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Coating (BaSO) does not integrate all the wavelengths in the same way

DES cube control

CCD cooled at 173K and at vacuum (10^{-6} mbar)

2 temperature sensors

Temperature controller gives a fluctuation of only 1K

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N₂ deposited

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LBL Design

- Sizes: 2kx4k, 2kx2k, 0.5kx1k
- 250 μm thick
- 15 μm pixels (0.27"/pixel)
- readout 250 kpix/sec, readout time ~ 17 sec
- **QE > 50% at 1000 nm**

$V_1 > V_2$

creating potential wells

- Due to the higher potential well, the hole is collected

Transfer process

Transfer process

Transfer process

Vertical clocking moves charge towards serial register

Horizontal clocking moves charge along serial output register to video output amplifiers

2 channels (U,L) to read each half part of the CCD

Over clocks are done to measure the dark current

Last gates of the serial register

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Horizontal clocking moves charge along serial output register to video output amplifiers

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Bias voltages table provided by LBNL

<i>Signal</i>	<i>Typical voltage (V)</i>
Substrate bias (V_{SUB})	40
Reset drain (V_{REF})	-12
Output transfer gate (V_{OTG})	3.5
Vertical clocks (V_1, V_2, V_3)	5.5, -2.5, 5.5
Horizontal clocks (H_1, H_2, H_3)	8.5, -3.5, 8.5
Output Summing well (V_{OSW})	-4

Charge is accumulated and a reading is done

- Clear image: to empty the wells
- Exposed image: shutter open
- Non-exposed image: shutter closed
- Reading: the transfer process starts

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Charge generation

ability to intercept an incoming photon through the photoelectric effect

Charge collection

ability to reproduce an image from the electrons collected

Charge transfer

ability to transfer collected charge from one potential well to another

Charge measurement

ability to detect and measure the charge collected in each pixel

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Test</i>	<i>Task</i>
Dark count	PTC	Charge generation
Linearity	PTC	Charge measurement
Full-well capacity	PTC	Charge collection
Amplifier's gain	PTC	Charge measurement
Pedestal	PTC	Charge collection
Amplifier's gain	MUON	Charge measurement
Diffusion	MUON	Charge collection
Charge transfer efficiency	MUON	Charge transfer
Energy Vs ADU	MUON	Charge measurement
Amplifier's noise	NOISE	Charge measurement
Charge transfer efficiency	CTI	Charge transfer
Charge transfer efficiency	XRAY	Charge transfer
Energy Vs ADU	XRAY	Charge measurement

	LBNL CCD performance	DES requirements
Pixel array	2048 × 4096 pixels	2048 × 4096 pixels
Pixel size	15 μm × 15 μm	15 μm × 15 μm
<QE (400-700 nm)>	~70%	>60%
<QE (700-900 nm)>	~90%	>80%
<QE (900-1000 nm)>	~60%	>50% at 1000 nm
Full well capacity	170,000 e ⁻	>130,000 e ⁻
Dark current	2 e ⁻ /hr/pixel at -150°C	<~25 e ⁻ /hr/pixel
Persistence	Erase mechanism	Erase mechanism
Read noise	7 e ⁻ @ 250 kpix/s	< 10 e ⁻ @ 250 kpix/sec
Charge Transfer Inefficiency	< 10 ⁻⁶	<10 ⁻⁵
Charge diffusion	6 μm	< 7 μm (*)
Linearity	Better than 1%	1%

- Automatic Tcl/Tk script to take the images for the tests (*MecStart*).
- 826 FITS images stored in the DES computer
 - Images:
 - Otg 140 images
 - Votgscan 196 images
 - Ptc 320 images
 - Noise 10 images
 - Cti 160 images
 - Other tests:
 - Xray about 100
 - Muon about 100
- A Linux script distribute the FITS in folders for each test, and execute the analysis tools
- Useful regions of FITS images are converted to text files with the ADUs of the pixels
- The results are plotted using ROOT

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CCD Testing Report

Device ID	pb-512-19
Type	Back Illuminated
Size	1024x512
Thickness	250 μm
Operator	Lluís Galbany
Analysis	Lluís Galbany

Results Analysis:

	Right Amp. (RH)	Left Amp. (LH)
Gain (ADU/e)	1.223 ± 0.000	3.118 ± 0.000
Noise (ADU)	12.410 ± 0.023	11.267 ± 0.020
Full Well Capacity(e)	~ 180000	~ 180000
Nonlinearity > 1% (s)	12 ± 1	9 ± 1
Output Gate for Charge Inj. Vref=-12V (V)	2.6 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.1
Minimal H+ for CTI requirements (V)	5.5 ± 0.5	6.0 ± 0.5
Minimal H- for CTI requirements (V)	-10.0 ± 0.5	-10.0 ± 0.5
Minimal V+ for CTI requirements (V)	1.0 ± 0.5	1.0 ± 0.5
Minimal V- for CTI requirements (V)	-10.0 ± 0.5	-10.0 ± 0.5
CTI calculus from Fe^{55} source	$3.13 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$4.01 \cdot 10^{-7}$

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A preliminary test to determine the operation region of the CCD

$$V_{EFF} = V_{REF} - V_{OTG-CI}$$

Images: 1 Clear + 20 sec exposed

for each pair (V_{OTG} from 0 to 9V, V_{REF} from -12 to -6V)

Mean signal as a function of V_{OTG} for each value of V_{REF}

OTG & VOTGSCAN tests

Plots generated.

From the values at which the charge injection occurs is plotted the output charge transfer plot

A new votgscan test is done, fixing V_{REF} to -12V and scanning V_{OTG} each 0.1V

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The photon transfer curve data is used to determine:

- the linearity
- the full well capacity
- the conversion gain (ADU vs electrons)
- pedestal

Signal in a pixel

$$S(\text{ADU}) = P Q_E S_V A_V$$

Incident photons emitted (n) → P
 Quantum efficiency (eh/n) → Q_E
 Sense node sensitivity (V/eh) → S_V
 Amplifiers gain (ADU/V) → A_V

Gain: number of electrons needed to produce one ADU

$$K = \frac{1}{S_V A_V} \xrightarrow{\text{Poisson}} K = \frac{S}{\sigma_S^2}$$

Images: 1 clear + 1 non-exposed + 1 clear + 1 exposed

For each exposure time from 1 to 40 seconds

Mean signal as a function of exp. Time
 Variance as a function of mean signal

Plots generated:

- Gain measurement
- Pedestal, well capacity & dark current
- Linearity

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Relation between signal in one pixel and the energy loss by a muon

Minimum-ionizing particles (MIP)

In Si: 270eV/ μm

3.65eV/electron

—————> 74 electrons/ μm

The most probable charge deposition in a 15 μm of Si, is 1100 electrons

(Maximum of 21.21 μm , 1555 electrons)

100 non-exposed images of 15 seconds, and hope to have good luck!
(+ master dark)

We have to subtract from the signal, the signal in a pixel that was not crossed

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17.2 μm \longrightarrow 1260 electrons
1408 ADU

$K=0.85$ electron/ADU

Measure of the noise generated by whole chain: read-out, thermal and shot noise

RMS of the signal distribution of the overscan region

Images: 10 consecutive readings

Average of the noise value
for the 10 images

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RMS of the signal distribution of the overscan region

Images: 10 consecutive readings

Average of the noise value
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Proper collection and transfer of charge in the potential wells: **Charge Transfer Inefficiency**

4 subtests, one for each value related with the transfer process (H+/H-/V+/V-)

$$S_i = \frac{\mu_{col,i} - \mu_{pedestal}}{\mu_{mean} - \mu_{pedestal}}$$

$$CTI = \frac{S_{i,last.col}}{256}$$

Images: 1 clear + 10 sec exposure

For each subtest, increasing 0.5V the appropriate voltage

Mean signal by columns in the transition to overscan region

CTI and noise is measured in each image

H+ example

Increasing the voltage of H+, the CTI improves

At some value the requirement is achieved

For low voltages the noise is too high

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At some value the requirement is achieved

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An alternative method to measure both the gain and the CTI

A source placed 2 cm in front of the CCD

GAIN

^{241}Am source used

Signal distribution

10 images of 10 second exposure

CTI

^{55}Fe source used

Histogram by columns

10 images of 10 seconds exposure

We plot the signal distribution for each 50 columns (in colors)

We can compare the number of ADUs of the peaks, with the energy of the peaks in the spectrum of the source (subtracting pedestal)

We take the mean value of the K α of each distribution
And normalize all to the first one
The slope is the CTI

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- We have developed a test station in IFAE lab to perform tests to the DES CCDs
- We have an automated way to take the set of images for the tests
- We have learned how a CCD test station works, and now we are able to be a CCD test station for DES and other projects